

Employers Feedback on the Soft and Technical Skills of Agribusiness Management Graduates

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Employer's feedback, Agribusiness, Graduates</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5103693</p>	<p><i>Employers feedback on the performance of graduates is one of the important indicators that the program is performing in the community. Bachelor of Science in Agribusiness Management (BSAM) is the flagship program of Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Lopez Quezon Branch, thus the feedback of the graduate employers was obtained. Descriptive design was used in the study and questionnaire was distributed to the employers. The results shows that 44% of BSAM graduates were employed in the agriculture and agribusiness industry. In terms of soft skills, employers said that all of the soft skills were highly important particularly willingness to learn and positive work attitude. They were also highly satisfied with the soft skills exhibited by BSAM employees particularly oral communication. Technical skills were perceived by the employers as incredibly important specially possessing theoretical knowledge in agribusiness while they are extremely satisfied with the understanding of industry standards and practices. High negative gaps were identified on the skills, the revision of the curriculum is recommended to be able to fully satisfy the gaps on skills and the requirements of the employers.</i></p>

Introduction

Employing graduates from different higher institutions are continuously practiced by different organizations and institutions in the community. Generally, employees' characteristics such as good communicators, good team players, with interpersonal skills with team values (Klazema, 2018) are needed by the employers. Aside from the graduate's knowledge on theories and practical aspects, soft skills are also needed by the employees for them to be hired by the organization. Soft skills such the ability to empathize with others, ability to manage time effectively and ability to communicate clearly are some of the much-needed traits of an employee and employers to continue with the organization. It has been said that these soft skills not only make the employee do the job but instead do it well. Employers observed that in an organization, soft skills such as listening skills, critical thinking skills and communication skills are mostly lacking in most graduates (Wilkie, 2019).

Polytechnic University of the Philippines (PUP) Lopez Quezon Branch is one of the 22 branches and satellite campuses of PUP. The Institution offers 13 Bachelor's Degree Program and one of those is the Bachelor of Science in Agribusiness Management (BSAM). In Quezon Province, it is the only institution offering the said program and this study aimed to: Determine the employer's satisfaction on the soft and technical skills of PUP BSAM graduates; Determine the Employer's Perception on the importance of soft and technical skills; Identify the skills which the BSAM graduates are lacking and; determine the skill requirements of employers in hiring BSAM graduates.

Method

This study used descriptive research method designed to gather information from the employers of PUP Lopez Branch BSAM graduates from 2016 to 2019. Of the 149 survey forms emailed to the employers of BSAM graduates, only 60 employers respond. The researcher used standardized questionnaire adapted from the study of Mehrotra and Elias (2017) with alpha coefficients of 0.89 for importance and 0.97 for satisfaction. The questionnaire was divided into 3 parts where the first part tells the details of the respondents such as the name of the Industry and its classification. The 2nd part was the satisfaction of the employer on the soft skills demonstrated by the employee and its importance in the organization. The 3rd part is the satisfaction of the employer on the technical skills demonstrated by the employee and its importance, and the 4th part is the perception of the employer on the skills and knowledge they require in hiring new employees. For the 2nd to 4th parts, a five (5) point Likert scale was used to measure the satisfaction and importance of the statement given. The gathered data were computed and analyzed using Frequency and Percentage and Weighted Mean in SPSS v 26.

Results and Discussion

I. Industry Classification

Bachelor of Science in Agribusiness Management graduates have a diverse career options. They could be in any field which requires knowledge and skills of a college graduate. Among the different industry classifications, majority of the BSAM graduates (44%) were in the agriculture industry (Fig 1). While, 19% are in Financial intermediation. The rests are in education, health and social work, manufacturing, motorcycle and personal and household goods and other community, social and personal service activities and public administration and defense.

Figure 1. Employment Industry classification of Agribusiness Management Graduates

II. Importance of Soft Skills and Satisfaction Level of Employers on the Soft Skills of BSAM graduates

Soft skills are those skills innate to an employee. Most of the organizations/institutions are looking for soft skills which could help the organization. As Wonderlic (2017) reported, many employers said that soft skills are more important than technical skills. As shown in Table 1, employers said that all of the soft skills were highly important. Willingness to learn and positive work attitude were the two soft skills which got the highest mean (4.82 and 4.72). They were also highly satisfied with the soft skills exhibited by BSAM employees. Among the soft skills, oral communication got the highest mean (4.88) while written communication got the lowest mean (4.40).

Table 1. Satisfaction level of BSAM employers and their assessment on the level of importance of the soft skills of BSAM graduates

Soft Skills	Satisfaction (x)	SD	Level of Importance (x)	SD
1. Teamwork	4.51 (Highly satisfied)	0.63	4.58 (Highly important)	0.64
2. Written communication	4.40 (Highly satisfied)	0.70	4.49 (Highly important)	0.68
3. Oral communication	4.88 (Highly satisfied)	0.69	4.66 (Highly important)	0.54
4. Time Management	4.62 (Highly satisfied)	0.69	4.65 (Highly important)	0.60
5. Positive work attitude	4.71 (Highly satisfied)	0.52	4.72 (Highly important)	0.52

6. Willingness to learn	4.61 (Highly satisfied)	0.65	4.82 (Highly important)	0.39
7. Resolve conflict	4.60 (Highly satisfied)	0.57	4.61 (Highly important)	0.59
8. Works independently	4.58 (Highly satisfied)	0.56	4.63 (Highly important)	0.53
9. Leadership skills	4.46 (Highly satisfied)	0.63	4.57 (Highly important)	0.58
10. Problem solving skills	4.49 (Highly satisfied)	0.63	4.58 (Highly important)	0.61
11. Collegial	4.47 (Highly satisfied)	0.65	4.49 (Highly important)	0.63
12. Accountability	4.57 (Highly satisfied)	0.59	4.60 (Highly important)	0.59

III. Importance of Technical Skills and Satisfaction Level of Employers on the Technical Skills of BSAM graduates

Technical skills are the expertise needed to perform specific task (Garry, 2020). In any workplace, knowledge of technical skills is needed. As shown in Table2, all the technical skills were perceived by the employers as incredibly important and possessing theoretical knowledge in agribusiness got the highest mean (4.54). In terms of their satisfaction, employees who possess an understanding of industry standards and practices got the highest mean (4.53) which mean that BSAM graduates were adept on the skills required of an agribusiness management student.

Table 2. Satisfaction level of BSAM employers and their assessment on the level of importance of the technical skills of BSAM graduates

Technical Skills	Satisfaction	SD	Importance	SD
Possess theoretical knowledge in the field of study	4.43 (Highly satisfied)	0.71	4.54 (Highly important)	0.69
Possess practical knowledge provided by the degree	4.42 (Highly satisfied)	0.75	4.46 (Highly important)	0.69
Possesses knowledge of specific computer applications	4.48 (Highly satisfied)	0.66	4.51 (Highly important)	0.68
Possesses an understanding of industry standards and practices	4.53 (Highly satisfied)	0.66	4.51 (Highly important)	0.68
Translates theory into practice	4.45 (Highly satisfied)	0.66	4.48 (Highly important)	0.65

IV. Soft and Technical Skills which Agribusiness Graduates are Lacking

Of the soft and technical skills identified, most of the skills show a negative employer satisfaction level (Figure 2). The gap score was measured by getting the difference of importance and satisfaction mean. A negative gap implies that that skill might not be enough since the mean importance is lower than the mean satisfaction. In terms of soft skill, only oral communication skill showed a positive employer satisfaction level while in technical skill, it was the possession and understanding of industry standards and practices that showed a positive employer satisfaction level. The three skills with the highest gap are willingness to learn, possess theoretical knowledge in the field of study and problem-solving skills. Though it showed that employers are highly satisfied with the skills of BSAM graduates, gaps still appeared. With this gap, it shows that continuous revision and expansion of competencies in BSAM curriculum are needed so that gaps in skills will be fulfilled.

Figure 2. Soft and Technical skills which are lacking on BSAM graduates

V. Knowledge and Skills Needed by the Employer

The need for trained and well-equipped graduates are needed in the workplace. As shown in Table 3, graduates who have an understanding on the technical knowledge required by the job is most needed by the employers. Knowledge in the field of study and computer applications are also extremely needed. While, understanding of industry standards and practices are needed but not much. According to the employers, this skill can be acquired by the employees once they are already in the institution/company/organization.

Table 3. Knowledge and Skills needed by the employer

	Mean	SD
1. Knowledge in the field of study	4.57 (Extremely needed)	0.61
2. Knowledge of computer applications	4.56 (Extremely needed)	0.63
3. Understanding of the technical knowledge required by the job	4.66 (Extremely needed)	0.54
4. Understanding of industry standards and practices	3.75 (needed)	0.43

Conclusion and Recommendations

Soft and technical skills are incredibly important to all employers of the BSAM graduates. The employers are also highly satisfied with the soft and technical skills of the BSAM graduates. However, the importance of those skills surpassed the satisfaction thus, gap on the skills of the BSAM graduates were identified. Only oral communication skills and understanding of industry standards and practices were identified to have a positive satisfaction level for the employers. Since high negative gaps were identified on the skills, the revision of the curriculum is recommended to be able to fully satisfy the gaps on skills and the requirements of the employers.

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